

METHOD OF DETERMINING THE AVERAGE PARTICLE SIZE IN GUNCOTTON PULP

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A method for determining the fineness of the guncotton pulp is described. The method is based on the principle of determining the relative specific surface area, by the rate of liquid flow through an assemblage of guncotton particles in a standard state of packing. The theory on which the method is based is discussed and it is shown how the relative figures obtained are dependent on the specific surface area and how they can be correlated with microscopic measurements of the average particle size.

The apparatus used for the experiments and the procedure of testing are described including the method developed for obtaining an assemblage of guncotton particles in a standard state of packing.

The results of actual plant tests are shown and a simplified apparatus for routine tests suggested.

An increasing number of industrial processes depend on an adequate control of particle size and various methods have been developed for controlling the particle size of powdered materials.

On the other hand, corresponding methods for pulp have not been developed to the same extent, and therefore the process of pulping still largely depends on "rule of thumb"

Attempts have been made to judge the fineness of pulp with an apparatus designed by Schopper and Riegler, wherein the "freeness" with which water parts from paper-pulp is determined; but as far as it is known here, nothing has been published regarding the scientific basis of this test.

Preliminary experiments carried out here have indicated that sedimentation methods as developed for powdered materials cannot be considered reliable when applied to pulp. The considerable amount of air enclosed in the pores causes conditions in which Stoke's law is inapplicable and bigger particles can be observed settling more slowly than smaller ones.

The only method which hitherto allows an estimate of the relative size and distribution of particles in guncotton pulp is the microscopic method. This method is slow and to a large extent dependent upon the human factor, but it does permit direct measurement.

Fig. 1 shows the broken up fibres of guncotton pulp after beating as they appear under the microscope. This shows a collection of agglomerated fibres and single fibres most of them being twisted. There is thus no possibility of determining an absolute particle size in guncotton pulp and all that can be done is to make relative measurements. According to the same fixed arbitrary procedure, we have, for example, measured the length of the circumscribed rectangle around each particle and Fig. 2 shows the distribution curves on this basis for pulp after different times of beating.

The microscopic method is, however, far too slow to be used regularly for controlling the process of beating. Sedimentation methods apart from being slow as well, are not at all reliable for pulp for reasons mentioned above and the "freeness" test is entirely empirical and arbitrary.

The problem has therefore been approached from a different angle and a test based on first principles has been developed here wherein results can be correlated to the microscopic measurements. Our method is based on the determination of the relative specific surface area, as measured by the rate of liquid flow through an assemblage of guncotton particles in a standard state of packing.

The rate of liquid flow through the fine pores of a cake, formed by fibres after settling, is under certain conditions subject to Poisseuille's law for viscous flow. Whether or not these conditions prevail in our experiment cannot be said off hand, since neither average pore diameter nor the length of the pores is known and Reynold's number cannot be determined directly.

There is, however, an indirect method for judging whether viscous (laminary) or turbulent flow prevails, which is based on the following consideration :-

Assuming that the conditions of laminary flow prevail, then if a liquid moves through a tube of circular cross-section, Poisseuille's equation applies.

$$P = \frac{32L\mu W}{gD^3} \quad (1)$$

P = drop in pressure in lbs/sq. in., L = length of the tube in feet, W = velocity in feet/sec., μ = viscosity of liquid in lbs/foot/second, D = diameter of the tube in feet and g = acceleration due to gravity in feet/second.

$$W = \frac{PgD^3}{32L\mu}$$

Let " v " be the volume of filtrate per capillary collected per second at a pressure drop ΔP , then

v = cross-section area of the capillary $\times$ velocity.

$$v = \frac{\pi D^2}{4} W = \frac{\Delta P \cdot g \cdot \pi D^2 \cdot D^3}{32 \cdot L \cdot \mu \cdot 4} = \frac{\pi D^4 \cdot \Delta P g}{128 \mu L}$$

Considering the average properties of the cake and assuming that there are ' n ' capillaries of equal diameter and length corresponding to the average dimensions of ' n ' pores,

Then the volume " V " of liquid collected per second

$$V = nv = \frac{n\pi D^4 g}{128\mu L} \times \Delta P \quad (2)$$

For any particular cake n , D and L are constant.

For any particular liquid μ is constant at constant temperature.

$$V = \frac{n\pi D^4 g}{128\mu L} \times \Delta P. \quad \text{Let} \quad \frac{n\pi D^4 g}{128\mu L} = k_1 \text{ (a constant).} \quad \text{Then} \quad V = k_1 \cdot \Delta P.$$

By varying the pressure difference (ΔP) we may obtain the following set of equations for different rates of flow (V).

$$V_1 = k_1 \cdot \Delta P_1; \quad V_1 - V_2 = k_1(\Delta P_1 - \Delta P_2) \quad V_2 = k_1 \Delta P_2; \quad V_2 - V_3 = k_1(\Delta P_2 - \Delta P_3) \\ V_3 = k_1 \cdot \Delta P_3;$$

$$\frac{V_1 - v_2}{V_2 - V_3} = \frac{\Delta P_1 - \Delta P_2}{\Delta P_2 - \Delta P_3} \quad (3)$$

(Assuming that k_f remains constant for all pressure differences considered).

Equation (3) thus provides a means of checking the flow conditions through the cake. If equation (3) holds for all the pressure differences used, it can be safely concluded that in each case the flow is viscous and that n , L and D are constant throughout the pressure changes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus.—The experiments were carried out with the apparatus shown in Fig. 3. The apparatus consists essentially of a long glass tube F.T. with a brass extension piece attached to its end. The brass element contains a stainless steel gauze of 40 mesh. The glass tube F.T. is provided with a water jacket for maintaining constant temperatures.

There are two communicating vessels CV1 and VC2, which receive supply of water at any desired temperature, and in turn supply water to the filter tube at constant heads, which can be adjusted with the help of U tube 'U'.

Procedure

(a) *Fixing Position of Filter tube.*—In the first instance (in Fig. 3), the stopper is not in the position as shown but is disconnected.

The space below gauze 'S' was completely filled with water by attaching a rubber tube and funnel to the nozzle at C_1 , filling the funnel and tube with water and working it up and down to expel all the air. Then stop-cock ' C_1 ' was closed and filter tube F.T. filled up to the top with water and syphon 'A' was set, which connected F.T. with the communicating vessel 'CV1'. The three-way stop-cock was opened connecting it with 'U'. Then F.T. was adjusted until the water level coincided with mark 'H' on F.T. and mark ' P_2 ' on 'U'.

(b) *Filling of Filter tube with Pulp sample.*—Syphon 'A' was broken and the water in filter tube F.T. drained to an arbitrary level above the gauze. Stop-cock C_2 was closed. The sample to be tested was made into a good suspension and poured into the filter tube F.T., taking care to avoid the formation of air bubbles, while pouring. The suspension was then made up with water, approximately up to mark ' H_2 '.†

(c) *The Filter test.*—As soon as the sample had been completely washed into the filter tube F.T., a stop-watch was started and syphon 'A' was set on to the tube when the pulp had settled away from the top. After 5 minutes stop-cocks C_1 and C_2 were opened simultaneously and the rates of flow recorded until the flow rate became steady. The space below the gauze 'S' contained air, since it had been emptied of water when stop-cocks C_1 and C_2 were opened. The filtration took place therefore at a head P_2 .

When a steady rate of flow has been reached, it is an indication that the pulp has

† The sample must be small enough to be completely washed into the filter tube F.T.

settled or in other words that the pulp has formed a cake of definite dimensions.

Before using this Filter test for comparing pulp of different degrees of beating, we have to ascertain, whether the different pulp samples after settling and applying different pressures fulfil equation (3).

The expression $\frac{\Delta P_1 - \Delta P_2}{\Delta P_2 - \Delta P_3}$ is a function of ΔP_1 , ΔP_2 , and ΔP_3 . These pressures have been kept constant through all our experiments. Therefore the above expression is constant.

For all our experiments this had the constant value of 6.06.

Table I shows how the value $\frac{V_1 - V_2}{V_2 - V_3}$, obtained from the flow rate measurements through cakes of guncotton pulp of different dry weights with filtered water* at a temperature of 20° compares with the theoretical value 6.06.

The results obtained differ with the exception of sample 5† only in the second decimal from the theoretical value. It can therefore be assumed that for the practical purpose of a plant test, equation (3) is fulfilled. This means that laminary flow prevails and further that neither 'D', the average pore diameter nor $n \times L$, the total length of n pores of average diameter 'D' have noticeably changed during our experiments. However, it may be pointed out that the experiments have to be always started at the highest pressure and ended with the lowest pressure. The reason for this procedure is that in going from lower to higher pressures a noticeable compression of the cake takes place, but if the highest pressure is applied initially, the recovery (expansion) of the cake on lowering the pressure is practically negligible.

TABLE I

Sample.	Dry wt.	V_1 at P_1 .	V_2 at P_2	V_3 at P_3 .	$V_1 - V_2$	$V_2 - V_3$.	$\frac{V_1 - V_2}{V_2 - V_3}$.	$\frac{P_1 - P_2}{P_2 - P_3}$.
1	33.6	33.4	13.5	10.2	19.9	3.3	6.00	6.06
2	22.12	49.6	20.0	15.2	29.6	4.8	6.1	6.06
3	28.8	37.0	15.0	11.4	22.0	3.6	6.1	6.06
4	36.56	31.0	12.7	9.6	18.3	3.1	5.9	6.06
5†	21.13	46.2	19.6	15.0	28.6	4.6	6.2	6.06
6	33.28	35.0	14.2	10.8	20.8	3.4	6.1	6.06

To determine the relative particle size in pulp, by correlating the average diameter of the capillaries with the average particle size equation (2) should be considered.

The right-hand side of equation (2) contains a second variable besides D , namely L , the length of the imaginary capillary, which is independent of particle size.

L can be assumed to vary proportionately to the thickness of the cake in the filter tube and consequently to its dryweight. This assumption is actually already inherent in

* The deviations are much bigger if unfiltered water is used.

† Sample 5 was taken after adding calcite. The calcite affects the capillary structure of the cake at different pressures.

this method of dealing with the cake as if it consisted of n capillaries with the average diameter D and the length L .

Therefore $L = k_2 W$, where k_2 denotes a constant and W , the dryweight of the sample, substituting $k_2 W$ for L in equation (2)

$$V = \frac{n\pi D^4 \Delta P \cdot g}{128\mu k_2 W} \quad \dots (2a)$$

$$V \cdot W = \frac{n\pi D^4 \Delta P g}{128\mu k_2} \quad \dots (2b)$$

The right-hand side of the equation (2b) is constant for any particular pulp, if the experiments are carried out at a constant temperature and pressure.

In practice it is very difficult to keep P constant for consecutive samples of G.C. as the thickness of the cake varies with W , its weight. This difficulty can, however, be overcome by determining the rate of filtration at two different pressure differences for each sample.

Assuming that the experiments are carried out with pressure differences P_1 and P_2 , then

$$V_1 \cdot W = \frac{n\pi D^4 \Delta P_1 \cdot g}{128\mu k_2}, \quad V_2 \cdot W = \frac{n\pi D^4 \Delta P_2 \cdot g}{128\mu k_2}$$

$$(V_2 - V_1)W = \frac{n\pi D^4 g}{128\mu k_2} (\Delta P_2 - \Delta P_1) \quad \dots (2c)$$

The pressure difference $\Delta P_2 - \Delta P_1$ can be directly read at the U tube of our apparatus (Fig. 3). The dry weight was determined by the density bottle method.

For carrying out quick plant-tests it is generally not possible to maintain the temperature strictly constant, and the results have to be corrected. Apparently the only factors in equation (2c) which are affected by temperature are the viscosity coefficient, μ and the pressure difference, $\Delta P_2 - \Delta P_1$. The latter is affected by the change in density with the temperature of the filtering liquid. In the temperature range proposed for conducting experiments, the change in density of the filtering liquid (water) is so small that it can be neglected. The change of viscosity, however, is appreciable.

It can be seen from equation (2c) that the rates of flow at different temperatures have to be inversely proportional to the viscosity coefficients at the particular temperatures.

Effect of Temperature on Rates of Filtration.—Under laminary flow conditions the rates of flow at different temperatures are inversely proportional to the viscosities corresponding to the temperatures.

t_1° = Temp. of water. μ_1 = Viscosity coeff. of water at t_1° . V_1 = Rate of flow of water at t_1° . t_2° = Temp. of water at t_2° . μ_2 = Viscosity coeff. of water at t_2° . V_2 = Rate of flow of water at t_2°

$$V_1 \text{ (at } t_1^\circ) = \frac{n\pi D^4 \Delta P_1 \cdot g}{128\mu_1 k_2 W}, \quad V_2 \text{ (at } t_2^\circ) = \frac{n\pi D^4 \Delta P_1 \cdot g}{128\mu_2 k_2 W}$$

$$\frac{V_1}{V_2} = \frac{\pi D^4 \Delta P_1 g}{128 \mu_1 k_2 W} \times \frac{128 \mu_2 k_2 W}{\pi D^4 \Delta P_1 g} = \frac{\mu_2}{\mu_1} \quad \therefore V_2 = V_1 \times \frac{\mu_1}{\mu_2}$$

In our experiments rates of flow have been corrected to 20°.

Some Results of Plant Experiments

For practical purposes the rates of flow through a cake of guncotton pulp in standard state of packing have to be correlated to the average particle size.

The rates of flow depend upon number n , average diameter D , and length L of capillaries in the assemblage of guncotton particles in a standard state of packing. On the other hand, D and L determine the specific surface area of the guncotton cake and it now remains to correlate particle size with surface area. Fig. 2 shows the distribution of guncotton particles obtained by microscopic measurements after different times of beating. As already mentioned, the length of the fibres was determined by measuring the length of the circumscribed rectangle around each particle. If we consider a bigger particle, it is obvious that in general the length of the circumscribed rectangle cannot be correlated to its specific surface area. The same length would be measured whether the particle consisted of one single fibre or of an agglomeration of fibres with a much larger surface area. Fortunately the position is not so unfavourable when the great number of particles involved in the process of beating is considered. Whatever the shortcomings of the microscopic measurements described above may be, the fact remains that the fraction of particles of small size, counted under the microscope, increases with the time of beating (*vide* Fig. 2 and Table II).

The increase of the fraction containing small fibres, compared with the fractions with bigger fibres, implies an *increase of specific surface area with the time of beating*, since any kind of breaking up of particles into smaller ones can only have this result. In this investigation we are not interested in the particle size of a single individual fibre but in the average size of a great number of particles. As the *average particle size* decreases, the specific surface area increases and in this fact lies the justification for correlating the rates of flow determined by the filtration method with the average particle size of guncotton assemblage determined by microscopic measurement.

TABLE II*

Duration of beating (hrs.)	3½	3¾	4	4¼	4½	4¾	5	5¼	5½	5¾	6
% Frequency of particles of sizes below 0.062 mm.	13.8	23.4	41.2	50.0	51.9	58.9	60.8	73.2	80.1	90.3	95.3

* Experiments carried out with small experimental beater.

In other words the figure $W.V.$ (dry weight of guncotton cake $\times$ rate of flow) can legitimately be taken as a measure of the degree of fineness of the pulp.

In our practical plant experiments we have used the expression $(V_2 - V_1)k(\mu_2/\mu^{20}) \times W$ as measure of the fineness.

V_2 and V_1 denote rates of flow at pressure P_2 and P_1 respectively; W , dryweight; k , instrument factor 10; μ_2 , μ at expt. temperature and μ^{20} , μ at 20°.

Table III shows some results of plant experiments with three different beaters. These indicate the possibilities of the filtration test in following the effect on fibre size of beating in an individual beater, and also in comparing the working of different beaters.

It is possible by controlling the process of beating with our apparatus to obtain pulp of the correct fineness and to decrease the average beating time. Further, any defect of wear and tear on the beaters affecting the process is indicated by abnormal results. The experiments were all carried out with the apparatus shown in Fig. 2.

For routine plant tests a simplification is suggested as shown in Fig 4, which is self explanatory.

TABLE III
Temp. of pulp = 20°.

Duration of beating.	Beater No. 7		Beater No. 8		Beater No. 9	
	$(V_1 - V_2)W \times 10.$	$(V_1 - V_2)W \times 10(\mu_2/\mu_1).$	$(V_1 - V_2)W \times 10.$	$(V_1 - V_2)W \times 10(\mu_2/\mu_1).$	$(V_1 - V_2)W \times 10.$	$(V_1 - V_2)W \times 10(\mu_2/\mu_1).$
3½ hrs	1199	1199	1118	1118	1116	1116
3¾	1023	1023	890	890	965	965
4	968	968	840	840	885	885
4½	856	856	850	825	938	953

The experiments were carried out in the Cordite Factory, Aruvankadu, Guncotton Section, between 1943 and 1945.

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